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Modelling of Strip Footing Problems Using Consistent Particle Method

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ABSTRACT

The Consistent Particle Method (CPM) is a Lagrangian particle method initially proposed to solve fluid dynamics problems, and has recently been expanded to the area of solid mechanics. The governing equations for mass conservation and dynamics of particles are solved by a predictor-corrector method. The spatial derivatives of variables (e.g. velocities and stresses) are computed by Taylor series expansion. The physical material density is directly calculated without the use of particle number density. In addition, no additional particles are required to model boundary conditions. For partially loaded boundary surface, the stress singularity problem due to sudden change of stresses is handled by the Inverse Distance Weighting method. Numerical examples of bearing capacity of strip footing as well as large deformation penetration of strip footing are presented to show the capabilities of CPM in solving geomechanics problems.

Keywords: particle method; Taylor series; geomechanics; bearing capacity; footing penetration

INTRODUCTION

The Finite Element Method (FEM) has been commonly used and shown to be effective in solving geomechanics problems particularly for those with small deformation. Nevertheless, there exist challenges for large deformation problems caused by severe element distortion. To address this issue, several advanced techniques have been developed which have their own advantages and disadvantages (Wang et al. 2015). An example is the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) which combines elements and particles for solving large deformation problems (Oñate et al. 2004).

An alternative to avoid the difficulties related to mesh distortion is to use meshless

43 methods which discretise the continuum domain by a group of particles. In this context, the
 44 Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) approach (Lucy 1977, Gingold and Monaghan 1977)
 45 has been developed in many areas including geomechanics (Bui et al. 2008). The SPH method
 46 calculates the derivatives of variables by using a kernel function for the approximation of Dirac
 47 delta function. Artificial viscosity is usually required for stabilisation purpose. The Moving
 48 Particle Semi-implicit (MPS) method (Koshizuka et al. 1995) has also been used to solve
 49 geomechanics problems (Inazumi et al. 2018). Based on Souto-Iglesias et al. (2013), the MPS
 50 weighting functions are indeed equivalent to the kernel functions used by SPH. A recent review
 51 of meshless methods can be found in Luo et al. (2021).

52 A relatively new particle method named the Consistent Particle Method (CPM) has been
 53 used to solve fluid dynamics problems (Koh et al. 2012), fluid-structure interaction (Koh et al.
 54 2013), multi-fluid interaction (Luo et al. 2015) as well as submarine landslide (Li 2017, Chow et
 55 al. 2019). CPM solves the Navier-Stokes equations with a predictor-corrector scheme and
 56 computes spatial derivatives of variables by Taylor series expansion, without using kernel
 57 function or artificial stabilisation term. Very recently, CPM was extended to the area of solid
 58 mechanics (Li et al. 2023). In this paper, a strip footing bearing capacity problem with small
 59 deformation using the von Mises model and a strip footing penetration problem involving large
 60 deformation with Tresca soil are presented to show the capabilities of CPM in solving
 61 geomechanics problems.

62

63 **METHODOLOGY**

64

65 **Governing equations and update scheme**

66

67 The simulation domain is discretised by a set of particles whose motions are governed by the
 68 mass conservation equation and dynamics (momentum) equation as follows:

$$69 \quad \frac{d\rho}{dt} = -\rho \frac{\partial v^\alpha}{\partial x^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

$$70 \quad \frac{dv^\alpha}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \sigma^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x^\beta} + a^\alpha - \mu v^\alpha \quad (2)$$

71 where Einstein notation is used, α and β denote the components of Cartesian coordinate, ρ is
 72 material density, t time, v velocity, x spatial coordinate, σ stress, a acceleration by body force,
 73 and μ material damping coefficient.

74 The Euler-trapezoidal predictor-corrector method of second-order accuracy is used as the
 75 time stepping scheme to solve the governing equations, and update variables at every step (Li et
 76 al. 2023). The stress components of each particle are calculated with the elastic-perfectly plastic
 77 constitutive relationship, involving von Mises model or Tresca model. Note that for the Tresca
 78 failure surface of a shape of hexagonal prism, the Lode angle should be adjusted at the corners of
 79 the failure surface (Smith et al. 2014). To ensure numerical stability, the time step (Δt) is
 80 determined by Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy condition (Courant et al. 1967):

81
$$C = \frac{V_w \Delta t}{L_p} \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

82 where C is Courant number, L_p particle distance, and V_w wave speed of material. For enough
 83 stability margin as well as good accuracy, a Courant number of 0.2 is applied in this study.

84

85 **Computation of variable derivatives**

86

87 The spatial derivatives of variables in the above-mentioned computational process are computed
 88 using Taylor series expansion. For 2D problems, the value of a differentiable function f at a point
 89 of (x_j, y_j) can be expressed with respect to a reference point at (x_i, y_i) as shown below:

90
$$f_j = f(x_j, y_j) = f_i + h_{ij} f_{,xi} + k_{ij} f_{,yi} + \frac{1}{2} h_{ij}^2 f_{,xxi} + h_{ij} k_{ij} f_{,xyi} + \frac{1}{2} k_{ij}^2 f_{,yyi} + O(r_{ij}^3) \quad (4)$$

91 where $h_{ij} = x_j - x_i$, $k_{ij} = y_j - y_i$, the comma in subscript represents partial derivative with respect to
 92 spatial coordinate, and $O(r_{ij}^3)$ is the third-order truncation error in which $r_{ij} = \sqrt{h_{ij}^2 + k_{ij}^2}$.

93 Applying the above equation to at least five neighbour particles in an influence circle
 94 with a radius of r_e , the spatial derivatives (i.e. $f_{,xi}$, $f_{,yi}$, $f_{,xxi}$, $f_{,xyi}$ and $f_{,yyi}$) of a variable at the
 95 reference particle i can be obtained through solving a group of linear equations (Koh et al. 2012).
 96 To promote computational efficiency, the candidate list method (Koshizuka et al. 1998) is
 97 applied to select neighbour particles from a group of candidate particles instead of from the
 98 whole computational domain, which significantly reduces the searching times. In order to ensure
 99 that there are a sufficient number of neighbour particles including those near the corner of the
 100 solution domain, an influence radius of $r_e = 3.1L_0$ is adopted, where L_0 is the initial particle
 101 spacing. Using more neighbour particles generally improves the computational accuracy, and
 102 leads to an over-determined equation system which is solved by the method of Weighted Least
 103 Square. The least-square weight used is $w_{ij} = 1/r_{ij}^3$ to give higher weights for particles nearer the
 104 reference particle and is consistent with the third-order truncation error in Equation (4). This
 105 approach is fundamentally different from other particle methods that use kernel function to
 106 compute spatial derivatives.

107

108 **Boundary conditions**

109

110 An advantage of using Taylor series expansion in the computation of spatial derivatives is that it
 111 is not necessary to use a full influence circle for neighbour particles. When imposing the
 112 boundary conditions (e.g. walls), additional particles, for example, mirror or ghost particles, are
 113 not added outside the boundaries. Instead, the velocity boundary conditions and stress boundary
 114 conditions are directly assigned to the boundary particles. In some geomechanics problems,
 115 stress singularity exists at the edge of a rigid strip footing (Sinclair 2004). To address this issue,
 116 the method of Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) is adopted herein with a modification of
 117 localisation to improve the computational efficiency (Li et al. 2023). The method calculates a
 118 variable at a point using a distance-weighted average value of other nearby particles.

119

Material damping

Artificial damping or artificial viscosity is not required in CPM. Mass proportional damping is adopted to model the (physical) material damping of soil in this study. The material damping coefficient (Equation (2)) is given by $\mu = 2\zeta\omega$, where ζ is damping ratio and ω the fundamental frequency.

Particle repositioning and removal

The particle displacements in large deformation problems can be considerable, leading to irregularity of particle distribution and influencing the computational performance of particle methods. To this end, two straightforward schemes for “particle repositioning” and “particle removal” are adopted in this paper for the strip footing penetration problem. These two schemes can be found in Li et al. (2023) for more details.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the capabilities of CPM in solving geomechanics problems, two numerical examples are presented herein: (a) bearing capacity of a rigid rough surface strip footing on von Mises soil and (b) penetration of a rigid rough strip footing into Tresca soil.

Example 1: Bearing capacity of strip footing on soil modelled by von Mises criterion

A strip footing bearing capacity problem as shown in Figure 1 is studied, in which the plane strain soil stratum is of width $L = 20$ m and depth $d = 5$ m, and the footing of width $B = 2$ m. Only the right half is simulated with $v_x = 0$ and $\sigma_{xy} = 0$ assigned to the particles on the symmetric boundary. The bottom boundary is fixed ($v_x = 0$, $v_y = 0$) and the right boundary is sliding ($v_x = 0$, $\sigma_{xy} = 0$). The rigid rough strip footing is modelled by imposing the prescribed velocity (Figure 1) to the top boundary in contact with the footing. Non-slip condition is assumed, i.e. there is no relative movement between the footing and the contacted soil. The free surface is simulated by applying the above-mentioned method of IDW to all the free surface particles. The stress free boundary conditions at the horizontal free surface are $\sigma_{yy} = 0$ and $\sigma_{xy} = 0$. The soil parameters are: Young’s modulus $E = 50$ MPa, density $\rho = 2000$ kg/m³, Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.3$, undrained shear strength $c_u = 100$ kPa, and gravity load is neglected. The elastic-perfectly plastic material obeys the von Mises failure criterion (inscribed circle to Tresca failure surface). The time step is determined by $\Delta t = CL_0/V_p$, where $C = 0.2$, and the primary wave speed, $V_p = \sqrt{E(1-\nu)/[\rho(1-\nu-2\nu^2)]} = 183.4$ m/s, is adopted as the wave speed of material.

158
159 **Figure 1. Schematic diagram of strip footing bearing capacity problem**

160
161 The CPM model uses 101×51 particles. For comparison, the FEM results are obtained
162 using explicit dynamic analysis and updated Lagrangian method based on 100×50 four-node
163 elements in Abaqus software. The time step $\Delta t = 0.11$ ms and 5% material damping ratio are
164 used in both the CPM and FEM analyses. Figure 2 compares the stress-displacement results by
165 CPM and FEM as well as the analytical solution for the bearing capacity (Prandtl 1920) in terms
166 of the averaged σ_{yy} results beneath the footing normalised by c_u against the vertical displacement
167 of the footing. It can be seen that the CPM result is close to the FEM result and approximately
168 converges to Prandtl solution. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show similar σ_{yy} stress contours for FEM
169 (with the stress results smoothed by Abaqus) and CPM (without smoothing of stress results) at
170 the settlement of $D = 100$ mm.
171

172
173 **Figure 2. Bearing curve of surface strip footing**

174
175 **Figure 3. σ_{yy} stress contour at 100 mm footing displacement by FEM**

Figure 4. σ_{yy} stress contour at 100 mm footing displacement by CPM

Example 2: Penetration of strip footing in soil modelled by Tresca criterion

The next example involves penetration of a strip footing into soil modelled by Tresca failure criterion. The example was first studied by Kardani et al. (2015) using the Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) method and subsequently analysed by other methods such as Material Point Method (MPM) (Solowski and Sloan, 2015), PFEM (Monforte et al. 2017), implicit Smoothed Particle Finite Element Method (iSPFEM) (Zhang et al. 2018), explicit Smoothed Particle Finite Element Method (eSPFEM) (Yuan et al. 2019) and Strain-smoothed Particle Finite Element Method (SPFEM) (Jin et al. 2019). The Rigid Plastic solution obtained by the incremental limit analysis (da Silva et al. 2011) is commonly used as the benchmark (Zhang et al. 2018).

As shown in Figure 5, the dimensions of the plane strain soil stratum are width $L = 20$ m and depth $d = 10$ m. The width of footing is $B = 2$ m. As the problem is symmetric about the vertical centre line, a symmetric boundary ($v_x = 0, \sigma_{xy} = 0$) is used and the right half is analysed. The bottom boundary is fixed ($v_x = 0, v_y = 0$) and the right boundary is sliding ($v_x = 0, \sigma_{xy} = 0$). The symmetric, fixed and sliding boundary conditions are directly assigned to the symmetric, fixed and sliding boundary particles, respectively, to simulate the boundaries. The rigid non-slip footing is at the middle of the top boundary and moves downwards with the velocity presented in Figure 5. The horizontal movement of the soil particles contact to the footing is constrained. The top free surface and the inclined/vertical free surface formed by footing penetration are simulated by the method of IDW. Following Kardani et al. (2015), Young's modulus of the soil is $E = 100$ kPa, density is $\rho = 1600$ kg/m³, Poisson's ratio is $\nu = 0.495$, undrained shear strength is $c_u = 1$ kPa and the soil is weightless. $V_p = \sqrt{E(1-\nu)/[\rho(1-\nu-2\nu^2)]} = 45.9$ m/s is used for the time step $\Delta t = CL_0/V_p$, where $C = 0.2$. Mass proportional damping is applied using 5% material damping ratio.

205 **Figure 5. Schematic diagram of strip footing penetration problem**

206
 207 After a convergence study, the CPM model uses 81×81 particles and $\Delta t = 0.54$ ms to
 208 simulate the right half of the problem. Since the soil deformation is large due to deep penetration,
 209 the particle spacing for the soil beneath the footing and that outside the footing become
 210 significantly different, giving rise to highly irregular particle distribution and causing instability.
 211 Furthermore, when particles are too densely distributed (for example, in the compression zone
 212 under footing), some particles become redundant. To this end, the particle repositioning is used
 213 for modifying the particle distribution at each time step, and the particle removal scheme is used
 214 to remove redundant particles if need be scheme (Li et al. 2023).

215 The bearing curves obtained using ALE, MPM, PFEM, iSPFEM, eSPFEM, SPFEM and
 216 CPM are compared with the benchmark (Rigid Plastic) solution in Figure 6 plotted by the
 217 normalised resistance force V/Bc_u versus the normalised penetration depth D/B . The CPM,
 218 iSPFEM and eSPFEM results are similar to the benchmark solution while the other results are
 219 larger. Figure 7 presents the CPM particle distribution and the comparison of the free surface
 220 patterns obtained by CPM, PFEM, iSPFEM and SPFEM near the footing at the penetration depth
 221 of $D = B$. The soil heave obtained by CPM is similar to that by PFEM whereas the iSPFEM
 222 result shows a larger prediction and the SPFEM result presents a smaller one. Figure 8 shows the
 223 CPM results at $D = B$ for the σ_{yy} stress contour where the effect of footing compression is shown.
 224

225 **Figure 6. Bearing curve of strip footing penetration problem**

227
 228 **Figure 7. Distribution of CPM particles and free surface pattern near footing at**
 229 **penetration depth $D = B$ (symmetric boundary at $x = 0$, initial top boundary at $y = 0$)**

230
 231 **Figure 8. σ_{yy} stress contour at penetration depth $D = B$ by CPM**
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234 **CONCLUSIONS**

235
 236 A bearing capacity problem of surface strip footing and a strip footing penetration problem are
 237 presented to demonstrate the capabilities of CPM in solving geomechanics problems. The CPM
 238 method does not require additional particles outside the boundaries, nor artificial
 239 damping/viscosity for numerical stabilisation. The material density is directly calculated without
 240 using particle number density. The IDW method is applied to free surface particles to tackle the
 241 problem of stress singularity at the edge of footing. To avoid numerical problems caused by
 242 highly irregular distribution of particles, the particle repositioning scheme and particle removal
 243 scheme are used for large deformation problems. By comparison of computational results with
 244 several other methods, CPM has been shown to provide good stability and accuracy for the

245 geomechanics problems studied.

246

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251

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